

GEOSPATIAL ANALYSIS OF RADIOACTIVITY DISTRIBUTION IN ALLUVIAL SOILS OF THE KOLUBARA RIVER BASIN AT 20 CM DEPTH

VUK GAJIĆ¹, BORIS VAKANJAC², NIKOLA MILIĆ³

¹ Singidunum University, Environment and Sustainable Development, Belgrade, vgajic@singidunum.ac.rs, 0000-0001-6464-8226

² Military Geographical Institute "General Stevan Bošković", Belgrade, International Research Academy of Science and Art IRASA, Belgrade, borivac@gmail.com, 0000-0002-9429-6943

³ Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Serbia, Directorate for Agrarian Payments, Belgrade, nikola.milic@minpolj.gov.rs, 0009-0008-7870-8419

Abstract: *This paper presents a study of the spatial distribution of radioactivity in alluvial soils across the Kolubara river basin. A total of 136 alluvial soil samples were collected at a depth of 20 cm along the main course of the Kolubara and its tributaries and subsequently analysed for gamma radiation under laboratory conditions. The measured gamma dose rates ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$) ranged from approximately 0.12 to 0.41 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$, mainly exhibiting values around 0.20-0.25 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. Most recorded values correspond to the expected natural background radiation, while about 5% of locations demonstrated moderately elevated levels (above $\sim 0.30 \mu\text{Sv/h}$). The highest gamma dose rates were observed locally at several sites within the catchments of the Ljig, Tamnava, Ub, and Obnica rivers. In contrast, the lowest levels were registered in the downstream section of the Kolubara and the Jablanica sub-basin. Spatial GIS analysis (using quantile classification) revealed the absence of a simple longitudinal gradient-zones of higher values appear sporadically, likely reflecting heterogeneous geological substrates and/or localized radionuclide sources. However, certain "hot spots" warrant further investigation regarding the origins of elevated radioactivity to preserve environmental quality.*

Keywords: *radioactivity; alluvial soil, natural radionuclides, anthropogenic sources, Kolubara.*

1. INTRODUCTION

This material describes the spatial distribution of gamma radiation levels in alluvial soils of the Kolubara River Basin based on laboratory measurements of soil samples, with special attention to identifying areas with potentially increased levels of radioactivity and their origin (natural or anthropogenic). Natural background radioactivity in soil originates from radionuclides that naturally occur in the mineral composition of rocks and soils (primarily radionuclides from the uranium-238 and thorium-232 series, as well as potassium-40). Globally, average concentrations of these radionuclides in surface soil are about 400 Bq/kg for ^{40}K , 35 Bq/kg for ^{238}U (or ^{226}Ra), and 30 Bq/kg for ^{232}Th (UNSCEAR, 2000). Also, the average natural background radiation typically ranges from 0.05 to 0.10 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$; in residential areas, a level up to 0.30 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ is considered normal. These radionuclides emit gamma radiation, contributing to the natural external radiation level outdoors. However, the content of natural radionuclides can vary significantly depending on the geological settings dominated by magmatic and metamorphic rocks (such as granite), which often have higher levels of gamma radiation from the soil than areas with mostly sedimentary rocks.

In addition to natural sources, radionuclides enter the environment due to human activity. One of the most significant global anthropogenic sources of radioactivity was atmospheric nuclear testing during the 1950s and 1960s, as well as nuclear accidents (most notably the Chernobyl disaster in 1986). The long-lived fission product cesium-137, produced by nuclear explosions and accidents, remains in the environment for decades; even nearly forty years after Chernobyl, it can still be detected in trace amounts in soil and sediments (Drndarski & Križman, 1994; Steinhäuser et al., 2014). Specific industries can lead to so-called technologically enhanced naturally occurring radioactive materials (TENORM), where the concentration of natural radionuclides in a material is increased by human activity. An example of TENORM is the exploitation and burning of coal. Coal contains natural radionuclides (^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th , ^{40}K), which are concentrated in ash during combustion.

Alluvial plains of rivers are specific areas when it comes to radionuclide distribution. Due to periodic flooding and sediment deposition, natural and residual artificial radionuclides distribution in alluvial soils can

be heterogeneous. The Kolubara River and its tributaries form a broad alluvial valley in western and central Serbia. Kolubara originates from the merging of the Obnica and Jablanica rivers in Valjevo. Stretching approximately 123 km, it flows into the Sava River near Obrenovac. Its basin includes numerous smaller and larger tributaries, such as Gradac, Peštan, Ljig, Tamnava, Turija, Beljanica, Ub, Lukavica, Rabas, Kladnica, Toplica, and others. The valley of Kolubara and its tributaries is mainly composed of Quaternary alluvial sediments (sand, gravel, clay) that make up fertile agricultural land. Serbia's largest coal mining basin, the Kolubara coal basin near Lazarevac, with several open-pit mines (Field D, Tamnava Field, etc.) and accompanying coal-fired thermal power plants, is also located in this region. This combination makes the Kolubara basin interesting for exploration of radioactivity distribution: there are typical natural radionuclides in the alluvial ecosystem; also, there are potential anthropogenic influences from industry (mining, energy production) and residual radioactivity originating from global nuclear events. Previous studies have addressed the content of radionuclides in Kolubara lignite and the local environment (Djurašević et al., 2014; Krneta Nikolić et al., 2016), as well as the mineral composition of Kolubara sediments and the natural radioactivity within them (Šaponjić et al., 2022).

2. METHODOLOGY

Sampling was carried out at 136 locations distributed along alluvial terraces and the banks of the main course and tributaries at intervals of approximately 2 km (Figure 1). At each site, a sample of the surface soil layer was collected from about 20 cm depth (digging a small pit). Each sample (~1 kg) was packed and transported to the laboratory for measurement. All measurements were performed in laboratory conditions using a calibrated portable digital gamma-radiometer with a Geiger-Müller detector (Gamma-scout), designed for measuring the ambient dose equivalent rate of gamma radiation ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$). A compact handheld device with a digital display and measurement stabilization function was used, with prior accuracy checks performed at reference points.

In the laboratory, the gamma spectrometer was positioned centrally within each soil sample under controlled conditions, simulating the natural environment of the detector surrounded by 20 cm of soil. The device was protected with a thin transparent plastic film to allow direct contact with the sample while preventing damage or contamination of the probe. Measurement for each sample lasted several minutes until the dose readings stabilized. Both the minimum and maximum registered dose rates were recorded during the measurement interval. The maximum stable dose value ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$) was used as the representative value for each sample. In this approach, the maximum rather than the mean value estimates potential external exposure. It enables the identification of local peaks in radioactivity, which may indicate the presence of environmental anomalies. In parallel with sampling, UTM coordinates of each site were recorded using a GPS device, enabling spatial analysis and visualization of results in a GIS environment.

The measured dose values ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$) for the 136 sites were analysed statistically to determine basic descriptive parameters—minimum, maximum, median, quartiles, variance, and so on (using Python/Pandas software). The resulting value distribution was classified by quantiles (e.g., defined thresholds for the lower quartile Q1, median Q2, upper quartile Q3, as well as the 90th and 95th percentiles) to distinguish relatively "low," "medium," and "high" categories of radiation levels within the dataset.

3. RESULTS

Based on laboratory measurements of gamma dose rates for 136 alluvial soil samples from the Kolubara River basin (20 cm depth), the recorded range of values was from 0.121 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ (the lowest) to 0.405 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$ (the highest). The minimum registered dose was about 0.12 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$, and the maximum was about 0.41 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. The mean value for the entire dataset was not used in the analysis (due to the nonlinear distribution of data), while the median was 0.215 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$.

A histogram of the frequency of measured doses shows that most locations (over 60% of samples) have gamma doses in the range of approximately 0.20–0.25 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. A smaller portion of the sites (about 18%) have lower values, between approximately 0.16 and 0.19 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$, while about 16% of the samples exceed 0.25 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. Only a small number of isolated cases (around 7% of all samples) show higher values above 0.30 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. In other words, most measurement sites display stable and moderate dose values, while elevated levels appear rarely and at specific points (Figure 2). The highest recorded dose rates were identified in ten locations with the highest measured dose values. These locations and the corresponding maximum doses are listed in Table 1.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of maximum gamma dose rates in alluvial soils of the Kolubara river basin ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$) at 20 cm depth

Figure 2: Distribution of measured gamma dose rates ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$) at 20 cm depth in Kolubara alluvial soil samples

Table 1: Highest measured values

Sample ID/location	Max dose ($\mu\text{Sv/h}$)	Lithological unit	Possible cause
Obnica 2	0.405	Paleozoic schists (metamorphic formations, Gradac basin)	Natural: high Th/U content in metamorphic rocks; minor industrial influence (distant mining sites)
Ub 7	0.375	Tertiary clay-schist formations (Kolubara basin)	Combined: local geology with increased K/U content; possible minor influence of power plant ash
Ljig 10	0.375	Palaeozoic limestones and schists (Ljig mountain slopes)	Natural: granite fragments
Kolubara 23	0.332	Quaternary alluvium (deposits from various sources)	Natural: sediments of mixed origin
Lukavica 3	0.317	Tertiary limestones (tributary of Ub, near a mine)	Natural: sediments with high concentrations of natural radionuclides
Kolubara 33	0.315	Quaternary alluvium	Natural: deposits of geologically diverse origin; possible mixing of materials with elevated K and Th content
Tamnava 10	0.315	Tertiary lacustrine sediments (Kolubara coal basin)	Anthropogenic: proximity to the Tamnava open pit
Peštan 7	0.315	Limestone formations (Valjevo region)	Natural: carbonate sediments rich in Ra/U
Ljig 4	0.315	Paleozoic schists (Ljig source area)	Natural: sediment material originated from rocks with high radionuclide content
Ljig 6	0.300	Paleozoic schists (Ljig source area)	Natural: sediment material originated from dominant metamorphic rocks and flysch

4. DISCUSSION

Natural sources and geological influences: The obtained results are generally consistent with the expected levels of natural radioactivity in soils for this region. The recorded values ($\sim 0.2 \mu\text{Sv/h}$, typically) correspond to background gamma radiation originating from the geological substrate, characteristic for areas with a moderate content of natural radionuclides. Globally, according to UNSCEAR reports, the average annual effective dose from natural radionuclides in soil is about 0.5–0.6 mSv/year outdoors (UNSCEAR, 2000). If our measured values of about $0.2 \mu\text{Sv/h}$ are recalculated to an annual dose, assuming 20% outdoor occupancy, the effective dose is approximately 0.35 mSv/year, comparable to the global average (UNSCEAR, 2000). Differences between locations within the basin can be attributed to variations in the mineral composition of sediments and the basin's geology. Kolubara collects sediments from geologically diverse regions, from limestone (e.g., the Gradac catchment) and flysch zones to tertiary basins with coal-bearing layers (Lazarevac area). Elevated dose values recorded in the Ljig River basin (see Table 1) could be associated with the fact that this area partly drains regions richer in natural radionuclides (possibly including fragments of granitic or other igneous rocks in the alluvium). Conversely, the lowest values in the downstream part of Kolubara are likely the result of large amounts of sediment deposited from various sources. Material may be poorer in natural radioactive elements and “dilutes” the overall radionuclide content in the soil at the confluence.

Anthropogenic influences: Elevated values at some locations may also be due to human activities that have led to localised enrichment in radionuclides. The impact of coal mining on the Kolubara basin and the operation of thermal power plants were also considered. It is known that coal ash contains higher concentrations of natural radionuclides (especially from the uranium and thorium series) compared to unburned coal (Habib et al., 2018). At open-pit coal mines, these radionuclides may enter the surrounding soil through dust and ash deposition or surface runoff. Previous studies around the Kolubara open-pit mines have found somewhat higher levels of natural radionuclides in soil; for example, Mitrović et al. (2013) reported that the radium equivalent in uncultivated soil near one of the mines was about 235 Bq/kg, the highest value recorded in their study (Mitrović et al., 2013). Such activity corresponds to an external hazard index of about 0.64, below the prescribed limit (Hazard Index = 1). Therefore, even at that site, no unacceptable risk to the public was found (Mitrović et al., 2013). The influence of fly ash from more distant thermal power plants should also be considered. The Kolubara A power plant (Veliki Crljeni) and the TENT A/B plants in Obrenovac (which use Kolubara coal) have operated for decades so that ash emissions could have contributed to the radionuclide content (such as ^{137}Cs , ^{40}K , ^{226}Ra) in nearby soils. However, systematic monitoring by the relevant institutes has shown no accumulation significant enough to alter the radiation background over time (Krnetić Nikolić et al., 2016). Accordingly, our data do not show a clear pattern of elevated values exclusively downwind of the plants or pits- some of the highest measured sites (e.g., Ljig 10) are located outside the direct influence of power facilities. Mentioned suggests that the contribution of current anthropogenic sources, if any, is mainly localised and relatively minor compared to natural variations. Besides industry, anthropogenic radionuclides from other sources may also be present in alluvial soils. The fallout following nuclear accidents (primarily ^{137}Cs after Chernobyl) contaminated surface soils throughout Europe in 1986. Some of that cesium was redistributed on alluvial terrain through erosion and flooding. Radioactivity measurements in Kolubara sediments in the 1990s showed trace ^{137}Cs (Drndarski & Križman, 1994). Today, almost forty years later, the contribution of residual ^{137}Cs to external exposure is minimal compared to natural radionuclides-probably only a few percentages of the total dose (Steinhauser et al., 2014).

5. CONCLUSION

The results indicate that the current level of radioactivity in the alluvial zone of the Kolubara River primarily reflects natural sources, with only sporadic and limited influence from anthropogenic factors. Compared to similar studies in other river basins of western Serbia (Dugalic et al., 2010) and studies from neighbouring countries (Gajić, 2022), the measured dose rates in the Kolubara basin do not significantly deviate-they fall within the range typical for natural conditions, with occasional local variations. The information mentioned is reassuring from a radiological protection perspective: the population of the Kolubara region is not exposed to elevated external radiation from the soil (Dugalic et al., 2010). The average gamma dose rates from soils in Nigeria, Ghana, Turkey, India, and China range from about 0.05 to $0.15 \mu\text{Sv/h}$. At the same time, in this study, slightly higher values were measured around $0.2 \mu\text{Sv/h}$ -primarily due to the specific measurement methodology (detection inside the sample at a depth of 20 cm, as opposed to standard surface measurements). Nevertheless, these values remain far lower than those recorded in rare areas of exceptionally high natural radioactivity, such as Ramsar in Iran, where dose rates may reach 1-5 $\mu\text{Sv/h}$. The results suggest that the

observed differences in radioactivity within Kolubara's alluvial soils are primarily due to natural geological composition, without clear evidence of significant anthropogenic impact.

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